

REPURCHASE INTENTION MODEL BASED ON CUSTOMER TRUST: EMPIRICAL STUDY ON HAJJ AND UMRAH ORGANIZING COMPANIES IN BATAM

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze and address research gaps in various previous studies. Furthermore, it was found that Customer Trust, as an intervening variable, does not consistently explain Repurchase Intention. These factors were the reason for conducting this study. This quantitative study employed the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis method using the LISREL application. The research subjects were umrah pilgrims from eight umrah and hajj organizing companies in Batam, with a population of 789 pilgrims. The results of this study indicate that all exogenous variables significantly influence the endogenous variables. These results are expected to assist management in organizing and maximizing Repurchase Intention through Customer Trust.

Keywords: Electronic Service Quality, Brand Image, Healthcare, Customer Trust, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION AND LITERATURE REVIEW

Indonesia has the fourth largest population in the world after China, India, and the United States. According to the 2010 Population Census by the Central Statistics Agency (BPS), Indonesia's population was 237.6 million, and according to the 2015 Intercensal Population Survey (SUPAS), the population of Indonesia in 2019 was projected to reach 266,911.9 million. In 2020, it will reach 269,603.4 million, and in 2021, it will reach 272,248.4 million.

This makes Indonesia the fourth most populous country in the world. With 87.18% of the population being Muslim, it is the most populous Muslim country in the world, comprising 24% of the world's 1.8 billion Muslims.

Based on the above data, Indonesia's population is predominantly Muslim, representing 87.18% of the 272,248.4 million, or 237,346.15 million people. As devout Muslims, we adhere to the five pillars of Islam, mandated by Islamic teachings, including the fifth pillar: performing the Hajj pilgrimage to the House of Allah.

Indonesia's Muslim population, which makes up 85% of the population, faces limited time to perform the Hajj. This is due to the quota limits imposed by the Saudi Arabian government. The Hajj pilgrimage presents a significant obstacle for Indonesians due to the long waiting list. Some people circumvent this by replacing the Hajj with Umrah or planning to perform Umrah while waiting for the Hajj.

According to data from the Ministry of Religious Affairs, the number of Umrah pilgrims in Indonesia reached 1.3 million in 2019 (<https://padangkita.com/ini-jumlah-jamaah-umrah>-

indonesia-ke-arab saudi-perharinya/www.nielsen.com/id/). This situation presents an opportunity for Umrah travel agencies to provide the best possible service to each pilgrim. On the other hand, prospective pilgrims are faced with numerous choices when it comes to Umrah/Hajj travel agencies.

Several cases have emerged in the past three years, involving embezzlement and fraud involving prospective pilgrims' funds, both by well-known and trusted agencies and less so. Many pilgrims are lured by the promises offered by some Umrah agencies, which have had a very detrimental impact on prospective pilgrims.

Some of the consequences of the aforementioned cases have resulted in delays and even cancellations of prospective pilgrims' departures. This incident has created a negative trend for other agencies not involved, therefore each agency strives to provide the best service to consumers. For most consumers, this is seen as a trial that must be accepted with grace and should not deter them from performing Umrah. However, they are more careful in choosing an Umrah service agency, considering the capabilities of the agency they choose. Therefore, it is very interesting to conduct research to identify the potential of prospective pilgrims in determining their plans for Umrah.

Therefore, travel companies and Hajj and Umrah travel agencies are crucial in facilitating the departure of Indonesian Muslims to the Holy Land for Hajj or Umrah. Currently, Hajj departures in Indonesia experience long queues, so if pilgrims register today, their chance to depart could be seven to ten years later. Therefore, this study was conducted only on Hajj and Umrah travel agencies accredited A, B, and C in the Batam area, specifically for Umrah services.

However, even though the COVID-19 pandemic has relatively subsided and Umrah departures have been reopened by the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the number of Umrah pilgrims should have increased, several Umrah and Hajj travel companies in Batam have experienced a relative decline in sales, indicating low repurchase intention.

Numerous studies have examined the impact of increasing purchase decisions. Repurchase intention significantly influences purchasing decisions (Ali, 2019). Wung (2014) in Ali, 2019, states that repurchase intention is a key factor in retention, often considered one of the most important aspects of relationship marketing. Meanwhile, Fauzi & Ali (2021) found in their study that product quality and price had a positive and significant effect on purchasing decisions. Product quality had no effect on repeat purchases, price had a positive and significant effect on repeat purchases, and purchase decisions did not mediate the relationship between product quality and price.

However, they did mediate the relationship between price and repurchase. This study's results indicate that repurchase intention had no effect on purchase decisions. Other studies have shown that purchase decisions significantly influence repurchase (Puspita, 2022). The analysis revealed an influence between the marketing mix and purchase decisions, psychology on purchase decisions, marketing mix on repurchase, psychology on repurchase, and purchase decisions on repurchase (Puspita, 2022).

Based on the studies mentioned above, there appears to be a gap between purchase decisions and repurchase intentions. However, the low purchase decision, indicated by the relatively low number of Umrah pilgrims departing (less than 10 pilgrims) at several Hajj and Umrah travel companies in the city, is likely due to low repurchase intentions.

This is indicated by data from a 2022 survey of several Umrah pilgrims, who reported relatively low intentions to reuse previously used Hajj and Umrah travel services. Initial observations (2022) showed that the average repurchase intention of Umrah pilgrims at Hajj and Umrah travel companies only reached an average score of 98.75 ~ 99, still below the standard score of 105. This indicates that repurchase intention to use Hajj and Umrah travel services is generally low, particularly in terms of transactional interest, referential interest, and exploratory interest.

Furthermore, several other studies have linked repurchase intention to internal and external consumer factors, including linking repurchase intention to various factors, including brand image and trust. According to Haryono, Suharyono, Fauzi, & Suyadi (2015), customer trust has a positive influence on repurchase intention.

Similarly, Miao et al. (2021) found that customer trust can drive repurchase intention. Based on the two statements above, it can be said that the low repurchase intention of customers or Umrah pilgrims at Hajj and Umrah travel agencies in Batam City is likely caused by low customer trust.

This can be seen in data from the Directorate General of Hajj and Umrah (PHU) (2022), the first departure of Umrah pilgrims after the pandemic, 419 people, mostly from Batam, but using travel agencies from other provinces, not from Batam itself. The continued low trust of Umrah pilgrims in Hajj and Umrah travel companies is

Meanwhile, Dheensa, Lucassen, & Fenwick (2019) stated that consumer trust in travel agencies during and after Covid-19 was determined by the company's ability to care about its customers' health (customer healthcare). Likewise, Rahman, Bag, Hassan, Hossain, & Singh (2022) stated that a travel agency's concern for consumer health (healthcare) can increase consumer trust and interest in purchasing the company's services. Based on the two opinions above, the low repurchase intention and trust of Umrah pilgrims in Hajj and Umrah travel agencies in Batam are suspected to be due to their low concern for their health (healthcare).

This can be seen in the lack of compliance of Umrah pilgrimage organizers sending pilgrims to the Holy Land, which should refer to the Decree of the Minister of Religious Affairs Number 719 of 2020. This regulation is a guideline for organizing Umrah pilgrimages during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Brand image, as one of the company's efforts to introduce distinctive characteristics that differentiate them from competitors, can impact consumer purchase intention. As found in Sari, Fauzi, & Rini (2021), brand image influences purchase intention. Brand image in services emphasizes both tangible and intangible elements (Tunjungsari, Syahrivar, & Chairy, 2020). This means that brand image is not only related to the name symbol but also the values inherent in the company.

A strong brand image can convey a message that shapes consumer memories of a product/service. Likewise, trust is also A company's reputation can represent a company's existence, with various capabilities to convince consumers that its products or services are reliable. A company's responsibility is to maintain integrity and convince consumers that its legal and bona fide existence is its strength. Trust is a crucial asset for companies in attracting and influencing consumers. For consumers, trust is the basis for determining product/service choices. Research by Liang, Choi, & Joppe (2018) found that trust influences repurchase intention.

Research by Upamannyu et al. (2015) showed a significant, positive correlation between customer trust and repurchase intention. Similar results were found when CSR was used as a moderator for the influence of customer trust and repurchase intention. Other research also demonstrated a significant, positive correlation between customer loyalty and repurchase intention. Another study by Wijaya, Farida, and Andriyansah (2018) revealed the mediating role of customer satisfaction on repurchase intention. These findings are expected to contribute ideas related to the development of models that strengthen repurchase intentions in online store customers. This has implications for website designers. Web design for online stores that can increase trust and strengthen repurchase intentions.

Setyorini and Nurgraha (2016) found that trust influences online repurchase intentions, and consumers' perceived benefits on Kaskus served as a significant intervening variable with a positive correlation. Another study, by Vigripat and Chan (2007), found that service quality has a positive effect on brand value and customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction was found to have a positive effect on recommendations but not on repurchase intentions.

Furthermore, they found that the primary factor influencing repurchase intentions and recommendations was brand trust, not brand image. Further research by Marina, Setiawati, and Salehati (2020) showed that e-service quality was in the good category and repurchase intention was in the very good category.

The relationship between e-service quality and repurchase intention was in the strong category, with e-service quality having a significant positive effect on repurchase intention. Ricky Jayaputra and Kempa (2022) found that e-service quality and e-trust significantly influenced e-customer satisfaction. e-customer satisfaction, e-service quality. Another result shows that e-trust significantly influences repurchase intention; e-service quality significantly influences repurchase intention through e-customer satisfaction.

Further results show that e-trust significantly influences repurchase intention through e-customer satisfaction among Shopee Food users. Research by Rahmania and Wahyono (2022) shows that e-service quality has a significant positive correlation with trust and satisfaction. Another result shows that experiential marketing has a significant positive correlation with e-customer satisfaction..

II. HYPOTHESIS

H₁: Electronic Service Quality (ESQ) influences Customer Trust (CST).

H₂: Brand Image (BIG) influences Customer Trust (CST).

H₃: Healthcare (HLC) influences Customer Trust (CST).

H₄: Electronic Service Quality (ESQ) influences Repurchase Intention.

H₅: Brand Image (BIG) influences Repurchase Intention.

H₆: Healthcare (HLC) influences Repurchase Intention (RPI).

H₇: Customer Trust (CST) influences Repurchase Intention (RPI).

ESQ = Electronic Service Quality
 BIG = Brand Image
 HLC = Healthcare
 SCT = Customer Trust
 RPI = Repurchase Intention

Figure 1: Research Framework Model

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is a descriptive study using a quantitative hypothesis testing approach. The research subjects were Umrah pilgrims from eight organizing companies in Batam City, spanning January 2022 to June 2022.

The number of Umrah pilgrims during the time series period, combined with the eight companies as cross-sections, resulted in a population of 789 Umrah pilgrims, as presented in Table 1.

The researcher then used proportional random sampling as a sampling technique. To determine the sample members, the researcher selected representatives from each company in the population, the number of which was adjusted to the number of subject members within each company.

To determine the minimum sample size required if the population size is known, the Slovin formula can be used for each company, assuming a tolerable sampling error of 5% (Sugiono, 2016), as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where:

n = sample size

N = population size, 1548

e = sampling error rate, 5%.

The total sample size based on the formula calculation above is 245 Umrah pilgrims, and the sample size for each company is shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1: Population and Sample of Umrah Pilgrims

No.	Umrah Organizer Company Name	Number of people		
		Population	Sample	Pre-Test
1	PT. Samira Ali Wisata	534	$(534/789) \times 245 = 165$	$(534/789) \times 30 = 18$
2	PT. Julian Kamsaindo	24	$(24/789) \times 245 = 8$	$(24/789) \times 30 = 1$
3	PT. Semesta AnitaSalam	27	$(27/789) \times 245 = 8$	$(27/789) \times 30 = 2$
4	PT. Ramanda Tour	24	$(24/789) \times 245 = 8$	$(24/789) \times 30 = 1$
5	PT. Alfa Kaza Mustika	16	$(16/789) \times 245 = 5$	$(16/789) \times 30 = 1$
6	PT. Costariondo	10	$(10/789) \times 245 = 3$	$(10/789) \times 30 = 1$
7	PT. Ameera Mekkah	122	$(122/789) \times 245 = 38$	$(122/789) \times 30 = 4$
8	PT. Alsa Panca Perkasa	32	$(32/789) \times 245 = 10$	$(32/789) \times 30 = 2$
Total		789	245	30

Operational Variables:

Table 2: Operational Variables

Variable Name	Concept	Dimensions	Indicator	Item Code
E_Service Quality (ESQ)	Is a service provided through a website to consumers to facilitate purchasing and distribution activities effectively and efficiently.	Efficiency (X1)	1. Easy-to-understand application	ESQ3
			2. Easy transactions	
			3. Accurate product information	ESQ4
			4. Timely processing	ESQ5
		Fulfillment (X2)	1. Feature availability	ESQ6
			2. Service availability	ESQ7
			1. Transaction speed	ESQ8
			2. Speed in handling customer complaints	ESQ9
		System Availability (X3)	1. Customer data security	ESQ10
			2. Transaction security	ESQ11
		Privacy (X4)		ESQ12
		Brand Image (BIG)	It is one of the things that consumers remember when buying a particular brand of product.	Favorability of brand association (X5)
2. The Hajj and Umrah travel company has a good reputation.	BIG2			
3. The Hajj and Umrah travel company is perceived positively by pilgrims.	BIG3			
Strength of brand association (X6)	1. Gaining positive experiences with previous Hajj and Umrah travel agencies that the pilgrim participated in.			BIG4
	2. Gaining positive experiences from others			BIG5
	3. The company communicates effectively with pilgrims about Hajj and Umrah products.			BIG6
Uniqueness of brand associations (X7).	1. Hajj and Umrah travel companies have names that			BIG7
	2. Product explanations are easy to understand.			BIG8
	3. Pilgrims can easily share Hajj and Umrah products with others for recommendations.			BIG9
Healthcare (HLC)	Is the extent to which services can provide health guarantees for	Serious Attention Or Thought (X8)	1. Commitment to serving the health of the congregation	HLC1
			2. Commitment to facilitating the health of the congregation	HLC2

	individuals and groups in improving desired and consistent health..		3. Always paying attention to changes in the congregation's health jamaah	HLC3		
		Protection (X9)	1. Always monitor the health of pilgrims.	HLC4		
			2. Always evaluate the health of pilgrims.	HLC5		
			3. Always provide protection to every pilgrim.	HLC6		
			4. Always require health protocols (5M).	HLC7		
		Responsibility (X10)	1. Availability of medical equipment and medical personnel	HLC8		
			2. Always ready to serve the congregation	HLC9		
			3. Always responsive to customer health issues	HLC10		
			4. Responsive in providing health services.	HLC11		
		Customer Trust (CST)	Customer trust adalah harapan para pihak dalam transaksi dengan organisasi mana pun selama pengalaman layanan dan bahkan itu berkaitan dengan risiko yang terkait dengan asumsi dan tindakan atas harapan tersebut oleh organisasi terkait.	Performance/ Cognitive Trust (Y1)	1. Trust in competence	CST1
					2. Trust in schedule accuracy	CST2
3. Trust in cost	CST3					
4. Trust in credibility	CST4					
5. Trust in fulfilling promises on time	CST5					
6. Trust in fulfilling obligations	CST6					
Affective/ Personality Trust. Y2)	1. Trust in the service experienced			CST7		
	2. Trust gained from fellow congregants			CST8		
	3. Trust in consistently good relationships			CST9		
	4. Trust has an emotional connection			CST10		
Repurchase Intention (RPI)	It is an individual's assessment of interest in purchasing a designated service from the same company again, taking into account his current situation and possible circumstances.	Transactional interest (Y3)	1. Interested in using the travel service again	RPI1		
			2. Will not switch to using another travel service	RPI2		
		Referential interest (Y4)	1. Always recommending the service to others	RPI3		
			2. Bringing other pilgrims to use the service	RPI4		
		Preferential interest (Y5)	1. Informing others about the benefits of the travel service	RPI5		
			2. Providing testimonials from other pilgrims	RPI6		
		Exploratory interest (Y6)	1. Always seek information related to travel services.	RPI7		
			2. Always connect worship with travel services.	RPI8		
			3. Always stay up-to-date on developments in travel services.	RPI9		

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

A. Analysis of Research Variable Description

Table 3: e-Service Quality Construct Model Suitability Index

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,96	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,060	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,92	Good Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,95	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 4: Brand Image Construct Model Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,054	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,93	Good Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 5: Healthcare Construct Model Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,033	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	1,00	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,94	Good Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	1,00	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	1,00	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 6: Customer Trust Construct Model Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,049	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,93	Good Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	1,00	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	1,00	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 7: Repurchase Intention Construct Model Fit Index

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,067	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,92	Good Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 8: Full Model Fit Index (Hybrid Model)

Goodness of Fit Indicator	Expected Size	Estimation Results	Conclusion
Absolute Fit Size			
<i>Goodness of Fit Index (GFI)</i>	GFI > 0,90	0,92	Good Fit
<i>Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA)</i>	RMSEA < 0,08	0,061	Good Fit
Incremental Fit Size			
<i>Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI)</i>	NNFI > 0,90	0,98	Good Fit
<i>Normed Fit Index (NFI)</i>	NFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI)</i>	AGFI > 0,90	0,88	Marginal Fit
<i>Relative Fit Index (RFI)</i>	RFI > 0,90	0,97	Good Fit
<i>Incremental Fit Index (IFI)</i>	IFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit
<i>Comparative Fit Index (CFI)</i>	CFI > 0,90	0,99	Good Fit

Source: Processed data

Table 9: Hybrid Model Measurement Analysis (Full Model)

Model Size		SLF	STD. Error (SE)	t_value	Privacy Construct (CR)	Extract Variance (VE)
Latent Variables	Manifest Variables					
<i>E-service quality (ESQ)/ES</i>	<i>Efficiency (X1)</i>	0,92	0,066	13,93	0,965	0,882
	<i>Fulfillment (X2)</i>	0,55	0,063	8,78		
	<i>System Availability (X3)</i>	0,47	0,070	6,74		
	<i>Reliability (X4)</i>	0,80	0,070	11,35		
<i>Brand image (BIG)/BI</i>	<i>Favorability of brand association (X5)</i>	0,76	0,056	13,49	0,972	0,921
	<i>Strength of brand association (X6)</i>	0,84	0,054	15,44		
	<i>Uniqueness of brand associations (X7)</i>	0,80	0,055	14,57		
<i>Healthcare (HLC)/CH</i>	<i>Serious Attention Or Thought (X8)</i>	0,85	0,053	15,92	0,972	0,920
	<i>Protection (X9)</i>	0,80	0,055	14,59		
	<i>Responsibility (X10)</i>	0,73	0,057	12,74		
<i>Customertrust (CST)?CT</i>	<i>Performance/ Cognitive Trust (Y1)</i>	0,75	0,057	13,23	0,956	0,916
	<i>Affective/ Personality Trust. (Y2)</i>	0,87	0,065	13,47		
<i>Repurchase intention (RPI)/RI</i>	<i>Transactional Interest (Y3)</i>	0,77	0,057	13,57	0,977	0,913
	<i>Referential Interest (Y4)</i>	0,75	0,053	14,10		
	<i>Preferential Interest (Y5)</i>	0,80	0,063	12,70		
	<i>Exploratory Interest (Y6).</i>	0,83	0,063	13,09		

Source: Processed data

Sub-Structural Equation 1

$$CT = 0.34*ES + 0.23*BI + 0.36*CH, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.43, R^2 = 0.57 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

(0.049) (0.050) (0.066) (0.051)
5.84 4.54 5.53 8.44

Sub-Structural Equation 2

$$RI = 0.48*CT + 0.27*ES + 0.14*BI + 0.14*CH, \text{ Errorvar.} = 0.22, R^2 = 0.78 \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

(0.059) (0.066) (0.056) (0.049) (0.049)
8.19 4.10 2.47 2.81 4.46

Figure 2: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) Standardized

Figure 3: Hybrid Model (Full SEM) t-Value

B. Research Hypothesis Testing

Table 10: Hypothesis Test Results

Hypothesis		Hypothesis Description	Path Coefficient / R^2	t_{value} / F_{value}	$t_{criteria} / F_{criteria}$	Test Results
H1	H ₀	e-Service Quality has no effect on Customer Trust.	0,34	5,84	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted. e-Service Quality Influences Customer Trust
	H _a	e-Service Quality does affect Customer Trust.				
H2	H ₀	Brand Image Does Not Affect Customer Trust. Brand Image Does Affect Customer Trust.	0,23	4,54	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Brand Image Influences Customer Trust
	H _a	Brand Image Does Not Affect Customer Trust. Brand Image Does Affect Customer Trust.				
H3	H ₀	Healthcare has no impact on customer trust.	0,36	5,53	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Healthcare influences Customer Trust
	H _a	Healthcare has an impact on customer trust.				
H4	H ₀	e-Service Quality has no effect on Repurchase Intention	0,27	4,10	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted e-Service Quality influences Repurchase Intention
	H _a	e-Service Quality has an effect on Repurchase Intention				
H5	H ₀	Brand Image Does Not Influence Repurchase Intention	0,14	2,47	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Brand Image influences Repurchase Intention
	H _a	Brand Image Influences Repurchase Intention				
H6	H ₀	Healthcare has no effect on repurchase intention	0,14	2,81	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Healthcare influences Repurchase Intention
	H _a	Healthcare has an effect on repurchase intention				
H7	H ₀	Customer Trust Does Not Influence Repurchase Intention	0,48	8,19	1,96	H₀ is rejected and H_a is accepted Customer Trust Influences Repurchase Intention
	H _a	Customer Trust Influences Repurchase Intention				

Source: Processed data

H₁: e-Service Quality influences Customer Trust.

H₂: Brand Image influences Customer Trust.

H₃: Healthcare influences Customer Trust.

H₄: e-Service Quality influences Repurchase Intention.

H₅: Brand Image influences Repurchase Intention.

H₆: Healthcare influences Repurchase Intention.

H₇: Customer Trust Influences Repurchase Intention.

V. CONCLUSION

Customer Trust is the dominant variable influencing Repurchase Intention among Umrah pilgrims in Batam City, and this variable also successfully mediates or explains its influence on the research problem, namely Repurchase Intention. Meanwhile, the dominant variable influencing Customer Trust is Healthcare.

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